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Employees with Low Pay in the Italian Regions in the Period 2008-2020

They decreased by 2.16% on average

Istat calculates the value of low-paid employees. The variable considers the percentage of employees with an hourly wage lower than 2/3 of the median one out of the total employees. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2008 and 2020.

Ranking of the regions by value of low-paid employees in 2020. Calabria has a value of low-paid employees equal to an amount of 19, followed by Puglia with a value of 17.6 units and Sicily with a value of 16, 1. In the middle of the table is Umbria with a value of 9.5 units, followed by Molise with a value of 9.4 units and Piedmont with a value of 9.2 units. Lombardy closes the ranking with a value of 6.9 units and Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 6.09 and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 6.3.

Ranking of the regions by value of the percentage change in employees with low pay between 2008 and 2020. Valle d'Aosta is in first place in terms of value of the percentage change in employees with low pay between 2008 and 2020 with a value equal at 37.5% corresponding to a variation from 5.6 units up to 7.7 units or equal to a variation of 2.1 units, followed by Veneto with a variation of 36.67% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6 units up to a value of 8.2 units corresponding to a variation of 2.2 units equal to +36.67%. Liguria is in third place with a variation equal to 17.11% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.6 units up to a value of 8.9 units or equal to a value of 1.32 units. In the middle of the table is Sicily with a variation equal to 3.87% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 15.5 units up to a value of 16.1 units corresponding to a variation of 0.6 units. Lazio and Abruzzo follow with a variation from an amount of 10.6 units up to a value of 10.8 units or equal to an amount of 0.2 units corresponding to a value of 1.89%. Campania closes the ranking with a value equal to -15.17% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 17.8 units up to a value of 15.1 units corresponding to a variation of -1.7 units. Molise follows with a variation from an amount of 12 units up to a value of 9.4 units or corresponding to a variation of -2.6 units corresponding to a variation of -21.67%. Sardinia closes with a variation from an amount of 13.8 units up to a value of 10.7 units corresponding to a variation of -3.1 units corresponding to a variation of -22.46%. The value of employees with a low pay check on average in the Italian regions decreased from an amount of 10.885 to a value of 10.65 units equal to an amount of -0.24 units corresponding to a value of -2.16%.

Low-paid employees in the Italian macro-regions between 2008 and 2020. In the North-East the value of low-paid employees grew from an amount of 6.9 units up to a value of 7.9 units or equal to a value of 1 unit corresponding to a variation of 14.49%. Considering the North, low-paid employees decreased from an amount of 7 units to a value of 7.8 units corresponding to a variation of 0.8 units

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equal to a value of 11.43%. In the North-West, low-paid employees decreased from an amount of 7.1 units to a value of 7.7 units corresponding to a value of 0.6 units corresponding to a value of 8.45%. The value of low-paid employees in the Central regions grew from an amount of 9.5 units up to a value of 9.9 units corresponding to a variation of 0.4 units equal to an amount of 4.21%. The value of low-paid employees in the Islands decreased from 15.1 units to 14.6 units equal to a reduction of -0.5 units equal to a change of -3.31%. The value of low-paid employees in the South decreased from an amount of 16.6 units to a value of 15.3 units corresponding to a variation of -1.3 units equal to a value of -7.83%. The number of low-paid employees in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 17.3 units to a value of 15.6 units, equal to a reduction of -1.7 units corresponding to a value of -9.83%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- *Cluster 1:* Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria, Tuscany, Veneto, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Trentino Alto Adige, Piedmont, Umbria, Marche, Lazio, Abruzzo, Molise, Sardinia;
- *Cluster 2:* Campania, Puglia, Sicily, Calabria, Basilicata.

From the point of view of the cluster average we can see that the value of Cluster 2-C2 is higher than the value of Cluster 1-C1. The following ordering of the clusters derives from this, i.e. $C2 > C1$. There is therefore a significant distinction between the southern regions and the central-northern regions in terms of the value of low-wage employees. However, there are three southern regions which have a dynamic of the observed variable corresponding to that of the Central-Northern regions, namely: Abruzzo, Molise, Sardinia.

However, if we set $k=3$ instead of $k=2$ we can notice a cluster structure that significantly recalls the distinction between Italian macro-regions, namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Lombardy, Trentino Alto Adige, Tuscany, Piedmont, Umbria, Marche;
- *Cluster 2:* Puglia, Campania, Calabria, Sicily;
- *Cluster 3:* Sardinia, Molise, Abruzzo, Lazio, Basilicata.

If we consider the value of the average of the clusters then we can verify the following ordering: $C2 > C3 > C1$. That is, it turns out that the southern regions tend to have a value of low-paid employees higher than the value of cluster 3 which also includes two regions of Central Italy, and also higher than the value of Cluster 1 which contains the northern regions to which they are also added the Marche and Umbria. We can therefore note that in any case the southern regions remain with medium-low values of the observed variable. The only regions in the Centre-South that stably converge on the values of the Centre-North are the Marche and Tuscany. However, we must consider that the choice to set a value of $k=3$ is suboptimal compared to the choice to set a value of $k=2$ in terms of the Silhouette coefficient. In fact, the value of the Silhouette coefficient of $k=2$ is higher than the value of the Silhouette coefficient of $k=3$. Therefore the correct representation of the clusters with the Silhouette coefficient is equal to $k=2$.

Conclusions. The value of low-wage employees has decreased on average in the Italian regions. However, the reduction in the value of employees with low pay was mainly because this value decreased in the Southern regions. In fact, if we compare the 2008 data with those of 2020 we can see that the value of employees with low pay checks grew in the North by a value equal to +11.43%

and in the Center by a value equal to +4.21% while it decreased in the South with a value of -7.83%. Particularly serious is the growth in the value of employees with low pay checks in the North-East with a value of +14.49%. However, the value of employees with a low pay check in the southern regions remains very high compared to the northern regions. The value of employees with a low pay check in the northern regions is equal to approximately 49% of the corresponding value in the southern regions, i.e. in Southern Italy this value is approximately double the value in the northern regions. Therefore, there are the following macro-phenomena that can be identified:

- The value of low-paid employees in the southern regions decreased between 2008 and 2020 by 7.83%;
- There is a gap between the Central-Northern regions, with a low value of low-paid employees, and the southern regions with high values of low-paid employees;
- The value of low-wage employees grew in the North between 2008 and 2020.

Workers with a low pay check can be assimilated to the working poor, that is, people who, despite working, remain poor. This is a new form of poverty which affects approximately 10% of employed workers in Italy and which could require targeted economic policies aimed at integrating the missing income compared to living standards on a local-regional basis. This condition is particularly serious because the working poor are very likely also people who experience other forms of social discrimination such as young people, women, people who have discontinuities in the job market, immigrants, and people with little education. It is therefore necessary for the Ministry of Labor to identify forms of intervention for poor workers so that an important signal is also given to the Italian population that it is possible to improve one's life by working. However, if incomes remain low it will be very difficult to convince NEETs, women, the long-term unemployed and immigrants to invest in the world of work due to low incomes and the impossibility of growing in the economic-social dimension.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

	2008	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
Veneto	6	8.2	2.2	36.67
Valle d'Aosta	5.6	7.7	2.1	37.5
Sicilia	15.5	16.1	0.6	3.87
Liguria	7.6	8.9	1.3	17.11
Puglia	18.5	17.6	-0.9	-4.86
Calabria	20.7	19	-1.7	-8.21
Lombardia	6	6.9	0.9	15
Toscana	8.3	9.1	0.8	9.64
Umbria	8.8	9.5	0.7	7.95
Abruzzo	10.6	10.8	0.2	1.89
Lazio	10.6	10.8	0.2	1.89
Emilia-Romagna	7.8	8.3	0.5	6.41
Basilicata	15.5	14.2	-1.3	-8.39
Trentino-Alto Adige	6	6.3	0.3	5
Campania	17.8	15.1	-2.7	-15.17
Piemonte	9.6	9.2	-0.4	-4.17
Marche	9	8.3	-0.7	-7.78
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	8	6.9	-1.1	-13.75
Sardegna	13.8	10.7	-3.1	-22.46
Molise	12	9.4	-2.6	-21.67

